

EXPERIMENT AND PREDICTION OF IN-PLANE LOCALISED CRUSHING RESPONSES OF CF/EP COMPOSITE SANDWICH PANELS UNDER A SEMICIRCULAR INDENTER

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the in-plane localised crushing responses of carbon fibre reinforced epoxy (CF/EP) composite sandwich panels under a semi-circular indenter subjected to both quasi-static and dynamic loadings. The in-plane localised crushing behaviours of the CF/EP composite sandwich panels were investigated. It was found that the specimens were prone to lamina bending under quasi-static compression, whilst the specimens failed mostly with fronds fracturing under dynamic crushing. The specific energy absorption (SEA) of the panels under dynamic impact is 25.5% lower than that under quasi-static compression. An energy balance model was adopted to analyse failure mechanisms and energy dissipation. To the model, the geometry of the debris wedge was predicted using an inverse calculation with experimental validation. The results showed that the crush energy was mainly consumed by friction work and bending.

1 INTRODUCTION

Currently, the CF/EP composite sandwich panels are utilised in a wide range of industrial fields, and several studies have been performed on them when being subjected to in-plane (globalised) crushing [1]. Nevertheless, instead of in-plane globalised loads, many of the accidental loads may locally crash into the panels, such as crashes at free edge stringers inside an aeroplane wing box, fasteners [2] and so on. Hence, the in-plane localised crushing, especially when under a semicircular indenter, is essential to be investigated.

The present study investigates the quasi-static and dynamic responses of the CF/EP composite sandwich honeycomb panels subjected to in-plane localised crushing using a semicircular indenter. The damage mechanisms and failure responses are investigated. An analytical model is developed based on the observed principal progressive crushing mechanisms for predicting and analysing the crushing responses.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PREPARATIONS

The CF/EP composite sandwich panels were made of three main sections: the plain woven T300 CF/EP composite face sheets, the honeycomb core and the adhesive. The ply sequence of the CF/EP composite face sheets is [(45/-45), (0/90), (90/0), (-45/45)] with a nominal thickness of 0.88 mm [3]. The manufacturing details and mechanical properties of the specimens have been described in our previous study [1]. The specimens were cut into 60 mm × 60 mm square shape. The semicircular indenter (with a radius of 8 mm) was manufactured under an overall size of 16 mm (width) × 30 mm (height) × 40 mm (thickness), as shown in Figure 1. Also, to prevent the specimens from unexpected buckling or other kinds of catastrophic failures, a specifically designed fixture was manufactured, and its constituent and fixing scenario are shown in Figure 1. It can be seen that all edges of the specimens were clamped

except for the crushing edges. After the tests, the specimens were machined and polished for SEM observation and assessment.

Figure 1: Experimental preparations.

The quasi-static tests were performed with a loading rate at 2 mm/min to characterise the in-plane localised crushing failure behaviours of the CF/EP composite sandwich panels under the semicircular indenter. The dynamic tests were conducted using an Instron CEAST 9350. The nominal impact velocity was set as 4 m/s, and the mass of the total impactor was measured as 5.765 kg. Then, the initial impact energy or the total absorbed energy E_a was 46.12 J, which can be further divided as follows,

$$E_a = E_s + E_0 \quad (1)$$

where E_s is the absorbed energy in the sustained crushing process, E_0 is the energy absorbed out of sustained progressive crushing. (Usually, the energy absorption capability is assessed within the sustained progressive crushing period [3]). Then, E_s can be integrated from the load–displacement curve for the progressive crushing stage.

$$E_s = \int_{S_0}^{S_1} F ds = F_m S \quad (2)$$

where F is the resistive force and s is the displacement; S_0 is the displacement when the sustained progressive crushing starts and S_1 is the final crushing distance; S is the distance for the sustained progressive crushing ($S = S_1 - S_0$), and F_m is the mean force. Then the specific energy absorption (SEA) can be expressed as

$$SEA = \frac{E_s}{A\rho S} \quad (3)$$

In the equation, A is the crushed cross-section area of the structural profile, ρ is the effective density of the material; Then, Eq. (3) can be transferred based on Eq. (2) into

$$SEA = \frac{F_m}{A\rho} \quad (4)$$

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Every kind of test was performed twice to guarantee the repetitiveness. Figure 2 depicts the load–displacement curves of the specimens under quasi-static and dynamic crushing. Under quasi-static compression, a gradual increment of the load within the initial period was observed before the indenter crushes to 8 mm; afterwards, the specimen was in a sustained progressive crushing (as shadowed in Figure 2) since the semicircular head had entirely crushed into the panel. It was calculated that the averaged mean resistive load within the sustained crushing area is 4.42 kN. When being subjected to dynamic impact, the load becomes more undulate, and the averaged resistive force of D-SH is 3.52 kN, which is ~20% lower than that of quasi-static crushing.

Figure 2: The response curves under quasi-static and dynamic crushing.

The SEAs of the CF/EP composite sandwich panels under localised sustained crushing and entire crushing are plotted in Figure 3. During the sustained crushing, the quasi-static crushed specimens are 25.5% larger than that under dynamic loading. When taking into account the entire crushing process, a significant drop of the SEA was observed compared to that within the sustained crushing period.

Figure 3: SEAs of the CF/EP composite sandwich panels between quasi-static and dynamic loading under sustained crushing and entire crushing.

3.1 In-plane localised crushing mechanisms

The in-plane localised crushed specimen is shown in Figure 4. A debris wedge with a tip angle α and side length l was observed, and the central crack led to the inward and outward splaying of the plies that were associated with massive interlaminar damages between the splayed bending fronds showing the common features for progressive failure as a lamina bending [1]. When under the dynamic impact, the specimens presented a scalloped end on the composite panel, the short interlaminar crack growth, and the almost completely ruptured fronds, showing a standard transverse shearing mode [3].

Figure 4: SEM micrograph of the specimen under a semicircular indenter subjected to in-plane localised (a) quasi-static and (b) dynamic crushing (A: intralaminar damage, B: interlaminar damage, C: bending).

3.2 An energy balance model

In this work, a theoretical model [4, 5] based on energy balancing was utilised for damage-mechanism and energy-dissipation analysis of the composite panel under in-plane crushing. In this model, three stages for the occurrence and development of the debris wedge of the composites under progressive crushing were introduced. However, the first two stages including the initial propagation of the interlaminar crack and the formation of a triangular debris wedge by pulverised material are exclusive of a sustained crushing period, and the total energy dissipation during these two stages is far less than that in the third stage - sustained progressive crushing, where almost all of the crushing energies would then be consumed [6], which results in four predominated failure mechanisms and the energy-absorption behaviours, i.e. intralaminar fracture, interlaminar crack, bending and friction. Then, the critical failure behaviours during progressive crushing were considered, and a schematic diagram [3] was presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5: The schematic diagram for the progressive failure of the CF/EP panel under in-plane crushing.

For the CF/EP composite sandwich panel, the energy absorption by progressive failure can be summarised as the composite panel failure W_f and the core failure W_c , which can be formulated as a consumed work.

$$E_s = W = 2W_f + W_c \quad (5)$$

Based on Figure 5, the work for the failure of CF/EP composite panel can be calculated as followings.

$$W_f = W_1 + W_2 + W_3 + W_4 \quad (6)$$

where W_1 is the work for intralaminar fracture, W_2 is the work for interlaminar crack, W_3 is the bending work, and W_4 is the friction work. The prediction model for the calculation of each work can be developed based on References [2, 4]. Also, by Eq. (2) and Eq. (5), the mean resistive force F_m can be calculated. However, the geometric parameters l and α for this model are important, but they are unknown. Here, we defined B_1 and B_2 as a function of the variation between experimental and predictive F_m under both quasi-static and dynamic loadings as objectives, respectively. Further, we utilised the inverse calculation to acquire l and α for prediction and analysis. The detail calculation equation and procedures can be referred from [3].

3.3 Validation and discussion

After inverse calculation, the optimal solutions of the Pareto front with the knee point (with the minimum distance D_{\min} to the utopia point or ideal point) are shown in Figure 6. The validation results show that the calculated values are greater than the measured ones, which is mainly due to the measuring difference caused by the "spring back" of the splayed fronds after unloading. Furthermore, the variation of F_m between the prediction and experiment is within an acceptable range, which is an indicator of the effectiveness of this tracking-back approach.

Figure 6: Optimal solutions of the Pareto front with the knee point and the validation results.

Based on Eq. (5) and Eq. (6), Figure 7 shows the energy dissipation of different failure mechanisms of the CF/EP composite sandwich panels under in-plane localised quasi-static compression and dynamic impact. Under impact, the percentage of the energies consumed by intralaminar and interlaminar cracking is slightly increased, while the underlying trend for energy dissipation is similar to those under quasi-static crushing. Under both the quasi-static compression and dynamic impact, the major contribution to the energy-absorption is the friction work, agreeing with the previous study [4] where the friction work would take in more than 50% of the total work done for energy absorption during in-plane crushing of a composite panel. Bending is the second significant contribution in energy absorption, being over 35% of the energy-absorption of the CF/EP specimens. The other two failure behaviours, e.g. intralaminar fracture and interlaminar crack, contribute slightly to the total energy absorption.

Figure 7: Energy dissipation of the specimens for quasi-static compression and dynamic impact.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the damage responses and crushing mechanisms of CF/EP composite sandwich panels under quasi-static and dynamic in-plane localised loads. It is found that, under quasi-static loading, the CF/EP composite sandwich panels were prone to a lamina bending, resulting in a number of splayed bending fronds associated with numerous interlaminar damages. In comparison, under impact, the specimens were dominantly damaged by transverse shearing, with obviously beforehand-fractured fronds. Regarding the energy absorption, the SEAs of the specimens under impact were 25.5% lower than that under quasi-static loading. An analytical model was developed for predicting the responses of the CF/EP composite sandwich panels under in-plane localised crushing. Also, an inverse calculation was implemented to recapture the geometric parameters of the debris wedge, and the prediction results were validated by experimental data. The energy-dissipation analysis indicates that the energy was massively consumed by friction work at over 50%, followed by bending at above 35%.

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